

The role of energy consumption prediction in Green Orchestration

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Abstract

This paper introduces a specialized profiler for energy consumption prediction and proposes a Conceptual Green Orchestration Pipeline that utilizes the profiler as middleware. The system’s architecture integrates a standard orchestrator (like Kubernetes) with a local ONNX model registry, targeting edge devices for deployment. Crucially, the profiler demonstrated strong performance, achieving 89% accuracy in selecting the optimal deployment device for resource-intensive models, a significant improvement over the 33.4% accuracy seen with random placement.

Keywords: Profiling, Green Computing, Edge, Placement, IoT

1 Introduction

In recent years, deep learning has advanced rapidly, becoming a key enabler for many Internet of Things (IoT) applications on edge devices. Platforms such as NVIDIA Jetson and Raspberry Pi are commonly used to deploy AI models in domains like agriculture, healthcare, and industrial automation [2, 16, 17]. However, the resource-intensive nature of deep learning poses significant challenges for deployment on constrained edge devices. While Ahvar et al. [1] show that fully distributed Edge systems can reduce energy consumption by 14–25% compared to centralized Cloud and partially distributed Fog architectures, mainly due to their nature of avoiding large-scale cooling and extensive intra-data center networking, this does not imply that running deep learning models on edge devices is free from high hardware utilization or increased energy consumption.

Consequently, many studies now focus on optimizing resource usage to lower computational and energy costs. Wadhwa et al. [26] outline three main strategies: task-based energy analysis, which models energy use per task to link

performance with consumption; workload scheduling, which applies queuing theory to balance workloads and minimize power costs; and efficient server allocation, which assigns tasks based on traffic and server speed to reduce packet loss and improve performance. Together, these methods enhance energy efficiency and system utilization.

Researchers have proposed various strategies to enable efficient deep learning deployment on edge devices, which face constraints in computation, memory, and energy. Liu et al. [12] discuss approaches such as lightweight model design, compression techniques, hardware-aware neural architecture search, and adaptive models that adjust to available resources. Another direction focuses on profiling to predict model efficiency across devices. For instance, Parra-Ullauri et al. [19] introduced a profiling and optimization framework that trains predictors—using XGBoost and MLPs, with XGBoost achieving an RMSE of 0.001—to estimate resource needs and guide layer offloading via deep reinforcement learning.

To achieve energy-aware deep learning orchestration, this paper integrates a middleware profiler into the deployment pipeline. By predicting a device’s power consumption based on its resources and the model’s features, it enables green orchestration in heterogeneous environments, improving energy efficiency while maintaining operational performance. It can be integrated into systems such as Kubernetes to inform deployment decisions. A related approach is GreenKube [25] by Theodoropoulos et al., which uses AI-driven orchestration with Deep Reinforcement Learning and Graph Neural Networks to optimize task offloading while considering resource use, QoS, energy targets, and network topology.

The rest of this paper is structured as follows. Section 2 reviews relevant literature and introduces key contributions in the field. Section 3 details the data collection process, the training of the profiler, and its intended usage. Section 4

presents the experimental setup used to assess the feasibility and performance of the proposed profiler. Finally, Section 5 highlights the broader implications of our work and its potential impact on future research.

2 Related Work

In recent years, profiling energy consumption on edge devices has gained significant attention, primarily motivated by the need to reduce electrical costs. This focus arises from the shortcomings of systems without energy-aware orchestration, which frequently lead to inefficient power usage and higher operational expenses.

As a result energy profiling on edge devices has been explored in several fields. For instance, in [11], Lee et al. propose an energy prediction system that combines deep learning with edge computing. IoT devices are used to gather energy usage data, which is then processed locally to reduce delays and ease the cloud workload. The system employs an LSTM network to predict daily energy consumption, achieving an average error rate of 27%. Based on the predicted data, users can monitor the status of electronic devices, detect anomalies, and analyze energy consumption patterns.

Geetha et al. [5] emphasize the need for energy-efficient strategies in green, energy-aware IoT networks that power smart cities, homes, grids, and industries. Given the energy constraints of IoT nodes, efficient renewable energy management and accurate load prediction are key challenges. The proposed GEQCC-FLP method combines clustering and future load prediction—using the Satin Bowerbird Optimizer for energy-, distance-, and delay-based clustering, and a Deep Random Vector Functional Link Network optimized with Adam for prediction. Simulations show GEQCC-FLP significantly outperforms prior approaches, reducing RMSE by 0.563 and MAPE by 0.687, demonstrating its effectiveness in optimizing renewable energy use in IoT networks.

Another example of energy consumption prediction from edge devices is presented by Savi et al. [23]. They propose a federated learning and edge computing framework for short-term residential energy forecasting. Rather than collecting detailed user data centrally, local LSTM models are trained on each user’s device using historical consumption, calendar, and weather information. These local models are then aggregated into a generalized predictor and redistributed to the edge. The framework can also group users based on similar consumption behaviors or socioeconomic characteristics to enhance accuracy. Simulation results indicate that this approach delivers forecasting performance comparable to centralized neural networks while significantly reducing training time, minimizing data transfer, and maintaining user privacy.

Zhu et al. [27] propose an intelligent edge computing framework for the Industrial Internet of Things (IIoT) to address the high energy demands of AI-driven applications.

Their heterogeneous architecture offloads AI tasks from centralized servers to edge devices and employs a heuristic scheduling algorithm for static scenarios, minimizing energy use while meeting latency and capacity constraints. Validated through testbed and simulations, the framework achieved significant energy savings—using less than 80% of static scheduling and 70% of FIFO scheduling energy.

A representative example of integrating green orchestration with predictive mechanisms is presented by Duy et al. [4], who propose a Green Scheduling Algorithm for cloud computing using a multilayer neural network to optimize server power consumption. By forecasting future workloads from historical traces, the predictor enables the scheduler to power down idle servers and reactivate them only when needed, reducing energy use while maintaining service quality. The neural predictor is lightweight and efficient, capable of training within seconds on large datasets and producing tens of thousands of predictions per second. Experimental results show energy savings of up to 46.3% with minimal performance impact.

Compared to previous studies, our work introduces a prediction model that performs energy consumption profiling by considering both the device’s current resource usage and the deep learning model to be deployed on it. Most prior research has not specifically addressed the energy load imposed by deep learning models on edge devices, as this represents a relatively new and emerging problem. By tackling this gap, our study can help the field move toward more energy-aware deployment strategies, enabling edge devices to host increasingly complex AI models without compromising efficiency. This contribution not only advances sustainable energy management in edge computing but also supports the broader development of scalable, green IoT ecosystems.

3 Methodology

This paper introduces a conceptual Green Orchestration Pipeline (Figure 1) designed to support the use of a profiler for energy consumption prediction. The pipeline is conceptual and could integrate a traditional orchestrator such as Kubernetes with a local ONNX model registry. The choice of a local registry is supported by Makris et al. [14], who showed that retrieving files locally can significantly reduce execution time and energy use. The orchestrator would forward the selected model to the prediction mechanism, composed of a Model Characteristics Extractor (MCE) and a Profiler. The MCE extracts model features, while the Profiler gathers device metrics such as CPU load, disk usage, and device type, potentially using a Prometheus-based monitoring named EdgeCloud Mon [10]. Using this information, the Profiler serves as middleware that determines the optimal deployment, while the orchestrator carries out the execution on edge devices such as the Jetson Nano and Raspberry Pi 4B.

Figure 1. Energy prediction in Orchestration pipeline

Figure 2. Input and output of the Profiler

In the proposed pipeline the profiling mechanism is the main intelligent core entity and acts as an assistant for the orchestration. Specifically, the profiler employs an MLP regressor model to perform regression analysis. The choice of MLP regressor is based on its capability of learning complex, non-linear relationships between input features such as model characteristics and device metrics. Compared to simpler regression methods, the MLP can better capture the variability of heterogeneous edge environments, leading to more accurate and generalizable predictions of energy consumption and performance across diverse hardware platforms.

The profiler estimates a model’s energy consumption using features that describe both the model and the device (see Figure 2). Model features include counts of convolutional, fully connected, and pooling layers, along with total parameters and input dimensions. Device features capture current CPU and disk utilization. To train the MLP regressor, a dataset was built from several state-of-the-art ONNX models covering key vision tasks such as image classification, object detection, and 6D pose estimation. The experiments were performed on a Raspberry Pi and a Jetson Nano, where each model was executed and performance metrics were gathered through a profiling script (see Figure 3).

A representative set of CNNs commonly used for image classification and object detection was selected, including AlexNet, DenseNet-121 [9], EfficientNet-Lite4 [24], GoogleNet (v1), MobileNet-v2 [8], ResNet-152, and VGG-16, all available from the ONNX model repository.¹ Additionally, the DeepLabv3+ [3] model within the EPOS framework [6] was included as a representative 6D pose estimation method, noted for its strong performance in the BOP 2020 Challenge [7]. PyTorch versions of RegNet [21] and ConvNeXt [13], along with the Keras² NASNetLarge [28], were converted to ONNX format. While most models were pretrained for 224×224 inputs, DeepLab used 640×480, and NASNetLarge was adjusted to 640×360 to match the Animal Kingdom dataset. Table 1 summarizes the selected models. Note that ONNX exporters from PyTorch and TensorFlow³ apply graph optimizations (e.g., node fusion, constant folding, node elimination [20]), which can cause slight discrepancies with reported architectures.

As most models were pretrained for animal detection, the Animal Kingdom dataset [18] was used for inference. In contrast, DeepLab was trained on IndustryShapes [22], an

¹<https://github.com/onnx/models>

²<https://keras.io/>

³<https://github.com/pytorch/pytorch/blob/main/torch/onnx/utils.py>, <https://github.com/onnx/tensorflow-onnx/tree/main/tf2onnx/optimizer>

Figure 3. Dataset creation process

Table 1. Model Architecture Characteristics

Model	ONNX version	Conv Layers	FC Layers	Pooling Layers
AlexNet	1.9	5	3	3
DenseNet-121	1.9	121	1	5
EfficientNet-Lite4	1.7.0	91	1	1
GoogLeNet (v1)	1.9	57	1	14
MobileNet-v2	1.2.1	54	1	1
ResNet-152	1.2.1	155	1	2
VGG-16	1.2.1	13	3	5
DeepLabv3	1.10.0	149	1	1
RegNet	1.18.0	74	1	1
ConvNeXT	1.18.0	40	73	1
NasNetLarge	1.17.0	488	1	57

RGB-D dataset of industrial tools and components designed for benchmarking 6D pose estimation. From each dataset, 100 test images were randomly sampled, and inference was executed 100 times per model per device to construct the profiling dataset. Among the models, DeepLab showed the highest computational cost, with inference times of 20–30 seconds. RegNet, ConvNeXT, and NASNetLarge also exhibited elevated inference times of several seconds, whereas the

remaining models completed inference within a few milliseconds.

During the inference phase for each model, the stress-ng⁴ CPU stress tool was utilized to impose load on the device. The number of CPU cores utilized by the stress tool and the applied load percentage varied across executions. To normalize the device load relative to the baseline hardware capacity, the load is calculated in the preprocessing step as:

$$\text{device_load_percent} = \frac{\text{stresser_device_cpu_cores} \times \text{stresser_load_percent}}{4}$$

Here, stresser_device_cpu_cores represents the number of cores under load during the execution, and stresser_load_percent is the load percentage per stressed core. The denominator corresponds to the total number of logical CPU cores available on the baseline devices used in this work, such as the Raspberry Pi 4B or Jetson Nano. This formula effectively converts the load measured per core into an overall device-wide load percentage, normalized against the total CPU capacity.

The dataset was preprocessed using normalization and encoding techniques. Numerical features were scaled with RobustScaler to reduce outlier effects, while categorical features (e.g., device type) were one-hot encoded. The target variable (energy consumption) underwent a log_{1p} transformation to stabilize variance, followed by standardization; inverse transformations restored predictions to the original scale. Within the neural network, Batch Normalization improved stability and convergence. The Profiler was trained only on CPU usage below 35% or above 65% to capture clear low- and high-load patterns while excluding noisy mid-range data.

4 Evaluation

This section presents experiments that demonstrate the effectiveness of the developed model. Each selected network was executed 100 times on both the Raspberry Pi 4B and Jetson Nano to collect performance metrics. Lightweight models with short inference times produced negligible power variations and were excluded from training. The Profiler was trained on more complex models such as DeepLab, RegNet, ConvNeXT, and NASNetLarge, which generate higher CPU loads and longer inference durations, resulting in more accurate power prediction.

The final model selected via 10-fold cross-validation demonstrated strong predictive performance. It achieved a MAE of 0.1755, MSE of 0.04913, RMSE of 0.2216, and an R² of 0.9826. The low MAE and RMSE indicate that predictions are consistently close to true energy values, while the low MSE shows that large deviations are rare. The very high R² demonstrates that the model captures nearly all the variability in the data,

⁴<https://manpages.ubuntu.com/manpages/focal/man1/stress-ng.1.html>

Figure 4. Metrics of the best trained model

Figure 5. Prediction vs Actual CPU energy consumption

effectively representing underlying energy consumption patterns. Figure 5 illustrates the close alignment between predicted and observed values. Together, these results confirm that the model is well-fitted, generalizes effectively, and can be relied upon for accurate energy prediction tasks.

The next step was to evaluate the best-trained model in a practical setting. For this experiment, each of the selected resource-intensive models was deployed on two Raspberry Pi 4B devices and one Jetson Nano, where inference was executed 100 times under varying levels of CPU load. The Profiler was then applied to predict the energy consumption for each model across 100 runs per device, with the goal of identifying the device that achieved the lowest power usage.

The Profiler’s performance was benchmarked against a baseline scenario in which models were randomly assigned

to devices. To be deemed reliable, it had to consistently surpass this random allocation strategy while producing predictions that closely aligned with actual outcomes. As presented in Table 2, the Profiler achieved an accuracy of 89% in selecting the optimal device for the tested resource-intensive models. In contrast, random placement attained only 33.4% accuracy. These findings demonstrate the effectiveness of the proposed profiling approach for energy-aware device placement in heterogeneous execution environments.

Table 2. Average Placement Accuracy

Profiler	Random Placement
89%	33.4%

5 Conclusions

This paper introduced a green orchestration pipeline that integrates traditional orchestration with power profiling to optimize AI model placement across ARM-based clusters. Profiler results show that models with higher computational demands and longer inference times are predicted more accurately, as they cause greater variation in performance and power consumption. In contrast, lightweight models show minimal variability and gain little from profiling-based placement. Thus, accurate power prediction is most beneficial for heavy models, enabling more energy-efficient deployment decisions.

In previous work, we explored predicting inference time using a profiler based on the XGBoost algorithm. Future research will aim to develop an enhanced profiler capable of simultaneously predicting both inference time and energy consumption using a unified model. Additionally, we plan to extend the profiler with optimization parameters to further improve orchestration efficiency. Our long-term vision is to design a profiler that functions as a gating network, inspired by the mixture of experts approach [15]. However, instead of selecting among multiple specialized neural network experts, our proposed gating network would determine the most suitable device for model deployment.

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